

EXPLORING INFORMATION RETRIEVAL BY LATENT SEMANTIC INDEXING AND LATENT DIRICHLET ALLOCATION TECHNIQUES

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Abstract : Today we are living in modern Internet era. We can get all our information from the internet anytime and from anywhere using a desktop PC or a smart phone. However, the underlying technology for relevant information retrieval from the internet is not so trivial, as internet is a huge repository of all different kinds of information. Moreover, data collection in the internet is growing exponentially and it is termed now a day as Big Data era. Retrieving the relevant information from the internet in the Big Data era is same as finding a needle in the haystack. This paper explores information retrieval models and experiments with the basic topic modeling concept of Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI) first and then with the more efficient topic modeling algorithm of Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA). Comparisons between the two models are described clearly and concisely in their efficiency in topic modeling. Various applications of topic modeling are also reviewed in this paper from the literature.

Keywords: Information Retrieval; Topic Modeling; Big Data; Machine Learning; Latent Semantic Analysis; Latent Dirichlet Allocation; Document Similarity; exploring;

I. INTRODUCTION AND OVERVIEW

The modern internet is a huge store house of documents, books, journals, digital libraries, e-mails, web pages for news articles, Wikipedia, medical dictionary, mathematics tutorials, social media blogs, comments and all others we can imagine of. Now a day's most of the businesses have online presence and government services are also uploaded in the internet for convenience, causing information overload. All this information can be in many different formats such as texts, images, audios and videos. Many interesting data patterns can be discovered in this huge storehouse of data that can be profitably utilized as business intelligence. Finding novel pattern from data is called data mining. When the data is text, it is called text mining. In this age of information overload we need novel computer algorithms to process this huge amount of unstructured text data automatically, which are beyond human cognitive power [Feldman et al., 2007]. For systematic study, this broad text-mining field is divided into several sub fields like information retrieval (IR), information extraction (IE), text classification, topic mining, clustering, sentiment analysis, text summarization etc. Information retrieval is a much focused sub area of text mining which involves relevant document selection from the huge repository and then their ranking. Whereas searching for information inside the document is called information extraction.

This paper focuses on text information retrieval field only. Main objective of this paper is to explore evolution of information retrieval field culminating to probabilistic topic modeling, named Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) proposed by David Blei in 2003 [Blei et al., 2003]. Web search engines are the most important applications of information retrieval. Information retrieval process starts when a user enters a search query to a web search engine. Now the task of the search engine is to retrieve the query relevant documents only. As many documents can match totally or partially the search engine ranks the documents as per their relevance. After reading a document, a human can also judge whether a retrieved document is relevant or not. However, it is not possible for a human to read all retrieved documents to find out the most relevant ones. So automatic ranking of retrieved documents is necessary.

Thus, information retrieval field involves two things, first document selection from database and second their ranking with numeric score. Automatic information retrieval field involves natural language processing (NLP) with machine learning (ML) algorithms. Natural language like English has the problem of “synonymy” and “polysemy”. Synonymy means different words may mean the same thing like the words “ocean” and “sea”. Polysemy means same word may mean different things, like the word “bank” may mean river bank or financial institution or heap. Therefore, if the query words are tried to match exactly with the documents in the internet, the retrieval may not be that relevant. The problem of synonymy will retrieve less number of relevant documents whereas the problem of polysemy will retrieve more documents even though some of them are irrelevant. Moreover, all users do not always express a query effectively. In presence of all these possible nuances, the search engine is expected to function most effectively.

Text data mining is much different from traditional data mining of numeric data. Text data is semi structured or unstructured and differs from structured relational database model. In relational database management system (RDBMS), mainly numerical data is kept in rows of a table and a collection of tables are joined with primary and secondary keys. Structured query language, SQL retrieves results by joining tables. In text-documents there are no explicit relations between words or sentences in a document or between multiple documents. So the traditional SQL queries not applicable for text data mining.

The utter importance and complexity of the IR field, made researchers start the first text mining conference named TREC (Text Retrieval Conference) in 1992, to evaluate various information retrieval methodologies on very large collection of texts. Many leading research Centers were formed in prominent universities like Center for Intelligent Information Retrieval (CIIR) at University of Pennsylvania, Intelligent Language Processing System (ILPS) at University of Amsterdam, and Information Storage Analysis Retrieval at RMIT University etc. For the computers to process and analyze the semi structured or unstructured text data automatically and efficiently, the text data is first transformed into structured data and is represented by various models. Wikipedia lists various document representation models that exist in the history of the literature as shown in Figure 1 [Wikipedia 2011a]. Properties of each model and their mathematical basis are listed in Figure 1. In the next sections, some of these text representation models are elaborated along with the metrics that measure effectiveness of particular IR system techniques.

Figure 1: Information Retrieval Models taken from Wikipedia (2011a).

Before moving on to the next sections, here we take a sneak-peak on how Google like search engines retrieve query results so fast. In fraction of a second, it can retrieve millions of web pages for a query like “basketball bat”. Searching the query words in each document in the database is not feasible for a large database. For Google like search engine fast retrieval is possible only because Google maintains indices of all web pages in their data centers distributed all over the globe. A user query is sent first to the nearest data center. An index table is prepared beforehand in each data center, which keeps a sorted list of unique terms in the vocabulary. A crawler program visit websites and crawl through pages to create index terms for the search engine beforehand. In addition, every term keeps a list of documents where the terms have been used. This is called inverted index or term-index table. This index table is searched for the query terms. If the search finds the query words in the index table, then it is redirected to the actual web pages to be fetched. The index table itself is quite large like 100 PB or so. Each data center can parallel process the query with many computers in that data center. The results are sent to the master node in the data center, which ranks them with numeric scores and send them back to the user’s browser.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents background and setup for information retrieval research area. Section 3 presents Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) topic model. Section 4 presents Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) topic model. Section 5 presents literature review for various applications of topic model. Section 6 presents evaluation of LDA model. Section 7 concludes the paper.

II.BACKGROUND AND SETUP

Earliest IR model was set theoretic, which considered each document and the query as set of terms. Information retrieval will be relevant if query set is a sub set of a document set. This exact match of query is more like data retrieval than information retrieval and not very effective. Notion of relevance between entered query by user and retrieved documents by this system is either 1 or 0. Thus, this is called standard Boolean IR (BIR) model (Figure 1). Modern information retrieval system uses vector space model. Here a collection of documents is called a corpus. Breaking a document into a set or words or terms is called tokenization. For automatic processing, the corpus is represented as a term document matrix (TDM) where there is a column for each document in the corpus and a row for each unique term in the corpus. This is called a vector space model where each column vector is a fixed length document vector and each row vector is a fixed length term vector. Thus for automatic machine learning, variable length documents are transformed into fixed dimension vectors in vector space model (Figure 1). This way, unstructured text corpus gets converted into structured data model. Vector space model also means bag of words concept, where word ordering is not important. In Vector space model, document ordering is also not important. Google's index table at each datacenter is equivalent to this TDM representation of the corpus.

In Boolean representation of terms, a cell in TDM may represent presence or absence of the term in a document by 1 or 0. Alternatively, a cell may contain the frequency of the term in a particular document called, term frequency (TF), where a larger frequency means a more important term. However, there are many terms in English language like (the, is, are, of, in, on, for, with ...) which are present in every document and has no particular importance in discriminating one document from another. These words are called stop words and are removed from the TDM to reduce document dimension. Also different tense of the same word like "work", "worked", and "working" have the same root so they all are treated as "work". This is called stemming of a term. More sophisticated lemmatization can be used in place of stemming for better results. In lemmatization, words are analyzed properly to remove inflectional endings only rather than just chopping off ends of words. For example in lemmatization "am", "are", and "is" are converted to "be". A typical TDM for the documents in the internet may have 100,000 terms and 1000,000 documents even though the TDM is very sparse, as all terms don't appear in all documents. Some dimensionality reduction of the TDM is achieved by eliminating the stop words and by stemming. In addition, term frequency (TF) of a TDM is weighted with another measure called inverse document frequency (IDF). As occurrence of a term in many documents reduces its discriminative power, the TF is weighted with IDF. IDF is expressed as $\log(d/d(t))$ where d is the number of documents in the corpus and $d(t)$ is the number of documents having the term t in it. Low IDF value means a term has less distinctive power as it occurs in many documents and it weights the raw TF value accordingly. Now each cell in TDM keeps TF*IDF quantity. An example TDM with eight terms and six documents is shown in Table1, with Boolean representation of terms for simplicity. The similarity between the documents or a query and a document can be measured by the angle θ between two document vectors. This is called cosine similarity measure. $\text{Cosine}(\theta) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i B_i}{\sqrt{A_i^2} \sqrt{B_i^2}}$ where A and B are two document vectors and i represents the term index in each document. When A and B are normalized to unit vector, cosine similarity between two vectors is the element wise dot product of the two vectors. When $\text{Cos}(\theta) = 1$ then the documents are exactly same. When $\text{Cos}(\theta) = 0$ then the documents are orthogonal. As each cell contains positive values only, $\text{Cos}(\theta)$ will never be -1 and hence documents are not exactly opposite of each other. In Table 2, cosine similarity matrix of example TDM in Table 1 is computed. Cosine similarity allows partial matching of query terms with document terms, unlike the naïve BIR model. In this vector space model, notion of relevance between query and retrieved documents ranks in the scale of 0 to 1, 1 being most relevant and 0 not relevant at all.

Table 1: Term Document Matrix (TDM).

Terms	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6
Ocean	1	0	0	1	1	0
Sea	0	1	1	0	1	0
Water	1	0	1	1	1	0
Boat	1	0	1	0	0	1
Ship	0	1	1	1	0	1
Fish	0	0	0	0	1	1
Whale	0	0	0	1	0	1
Shark	0	1	0	1	0	1

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6
D1	1.0000000	0.0000000	0.5773503	0.5163978	0.5773503	0.2581989
D2	0.0000000	1.0000000	0.5773503	0.5163978	0.2886751	0.5163978
D3	0.5773503	0.5773503	1.0000000	0.4472136	0.5000000	0.4472136
D4	0.5163978	0.5163978	0.4472136	1.0000000	0.4472136	0.6000000
D5	0.5773503	0.2886751	0.5000000	0.4472136	1.0000000	0.2236068
D6	0.2581989	0.5163978	0.4472136	0.6000000	0.2236068	1.0000000

Table 2: Cosine Similarity between Documents.

In Table 2, similarity between doc 1 and doc 2 is zero as they have no common terms between them. One disadvantage of vector space model is that cosine similarity measure could not detect that ocean and sea are synonyms. In the next section, another method named as Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) algorithm is described, which solves synonymy problem of vector space model. However, before going into that, here we present the metrics that evaluate the efficiency of information retrieval models first. The effectiveness of a model is measured by two metrics named precision and recall. Precision is the measure of number of relevant documents retrieved by the model out of all retrieved documents. Recall is the measure of number of relevant documents retrieved by the model out of all relevant documents in the corpus. A confusion matrix as in Table 3 is computed to find out precision and recall of an IR model.

Table 3: Confusion Matrix.

	Retrieved Relevant Docs	Retrieved Not Relevant Docs
Actual Relevant Docs	True Positive (TP)	False Negative (FN)
Actual Not Relevant Docs	False Positive (FP)	True Negative (TN)

From the confusion matrix, precision = $\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$ and recall = $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$. These two measures have the characteristic that when precision is high, recall may be low or vice versa. Thus instead of relying on these measures separately there is another measure called F-score which averages the above two measures by taking their harmonic mean and is more reliable, where F-score = $\frac{2*precision*recall}{precision+recall}$.

III. LATENT SEMANTIC INDEXING / LATENT SEMANTIC ANALYSIS

In a library books are grouped subject or topic wise, so it becomes easy for a user to find a particular book. However, in the internet there is no such physical organization of information topic wise. A topic is expressed as a group of words that occur together in a document or multiple documents. It is the machine learning algorithm which can try to find topics and topic proportion in each document so that document similarities can be measured more effectively as required for information retrieval from the internet.

Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI), is also known as Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA). LSI/LSA is a topic-modeling machine learning algorithm. A topic is a cluster of words that frequently occur together. These clusters are soft as they overlap with each other i.e. a word can belong to more than one topic. In LSI, indexing means attachment of metadata (or topic name) to the content terms. LSI/LSA addresses the synonymy problems of vector space model. LSA was developed by T. Landauer, P.Foltz and S.Dumais in 1990's at the University of Colorado's Psychology department [Deerwester et al., 1990]. LSA mimics human way of word grouping and topic categorization. A human will judge that in Table 1, there are fewer topics than number of words or terms. She may think that (ocean, sea, water, boat, ship) belong to one hidden topic named "aquatic vehicles" and (ocean, sea, water, fish, whale, shark) belong to a second hidden topic named "aquatic animals". In LSA co-occurrences of words in a document is statistically measured for hidden or latent meaning or semantics or topic determination and so is the name of the algorithm. LSA uses singular value decomposition (SVD) algorithm, which can factorize any matrix into three matrices. In SVD any $m \times n$ dimension matrix $A_{m \times n}$ is decomposed as $U_{m \times r} \Sigma_{r \times r} V_{r \times n}^T$ (Figure 2, Table 4), where r is the rank of matrix A , and $r \leq \min(m, n)$. In SVD decomposition U and V are ortho-normal i.e. $uv = 0$, $uu = 1$ and $vv = 1$.

Figure 2: Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of Matrix A.

When A , is a term by document matrix we can think of U as term by topic matrix and an element in U depicts how strongly a term belongs to a topic. U is an orthogonal matrix with left singular vectors of AA^T . Similarly V^T is a topic by document matrix and an element in V^T indicates how strongly a document relates to a topic. V is an orthogonal matrix with right singular vectors of $A^T A$. Σ is a diagonal matrix where singular values for A , are ordered in decreasing order (Table 4). Each singular value represents importance of the corresponding topic or semantic dimension in the corpus.

Now this SVD decomposition can be reduced to lower rank by eliminating the smaller singular values in Σ matrix and keeping only k larger singular values. This dimensionality reduction works as a noise removal by eliminating detail, less prominent topics of the corpus. In reality when the original TDM dimension is 100,000x1000,000, k value usually ranges from 100 to 300 to represent a good approximation of the corpus topics. The approximated matrix A_k is computed as $U_{m \times k} \Sigma_{k \times k} V_{k \times n}^T$. Thus a huge dimensionality reduction is possible in LSA where documents relate better to fewer prominent topics in the corpus. This way of using SVD for de-noising topics is called Latent Semantic Indexing or Latent Semantic Analysis. The cosine similarity between documents is again computed in Table 5, after SVD decomposition and dimensionality reduction to two dimensions ($k = 2$) only of the original TDM in Table 1. It can be seen in Table 5, that even though document 1 and document 2 had no common terms between them, LSA algorithm is showing some similarity between the two documents. LSA has figured out that 'ocean' and 'sea' are semantically similar by their co-occurrences with other words in the whole corpus. Thus, LSA reduces synonymy problem of the vector space model and improves recall measure. Similarly, we can also find out cosine similarity between different term row vectors from U matrix to find out term similarity.

Table 4: SVD Decomposition of TDM in Table1.

U (Term by Concept)						
	[,1]	[,2]	[,3]	[,4]	[,5]	[,6]
[1,]	-0.3294978	0.440979670	-0.43896910	2.886751e-01	0.03174022	-0.40438824
[2,]	-0.3076790	0.184947653	0.72784074	2.886751e-01	-0.15773889	-0.04890543
[3,]	-0.4492545	0.522752007	-0.08324904	4.843843e-17	0.25555202	0.38075079
[4,]	-0.3321821	0.048009946	0.05799231	-8.660254e-01	-0.02362650	-0.32831046
[5,]	-0.4791463	-0.400125147	0.24082535	2.375758e-16	0.27893098	0.25350132
[6,]	-0.2279526	-0.002949705	-0.07248834	-2.587991e-16	-0.90785373	0.12653797
[7,]	-0.2718449	-0.321593937	-0.43681605	1.020234e-16	-0.05662983	0.46733936
[8,]	-0.3593796	-0.481897484	-0.11489471	2.886751e-01	0.05511917	-0.53163770

Σ Diagonal Matrix (Singular Values arranged in decreasing order)						
	[,1]	[,2]	[,3]	[,4]	[,5]	[,6]
[1,]	3.6186605	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000
[2,]	0.0000000	2.085298	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000
[3,]	0.0000000	0.0000000	1.628531	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000
[4,]	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	1.414214	0.0000000	0.0000000
[5,]	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	1.256083	0.0000000
[6,]	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.5721684

V^T (Concept by Document)						
	[,1]	[,2]	[,3]	[,4]	[,5]	[,6]
[1,]	-0.3070035	-0.3167533	-0.4333886	-0.5220557	-0.36322671	-0.4616435
[2,]	0.4851784	-0.3342807	0.1705197	-0.1150362	0.54943201	-0.5555830
[3,]	-0.2850581	0.5242587	0.5793010	-0.5115677	0.08175116	-0.1998006
[4,]	-0.4082483	0.4082483	-0.4082483	0.4082483	0.40824829	-0.4082483
[5,]	0.2099111	0.1403660	0.2811261	0.4495824	-0.61962517	-0.5207141
[6,]	-0.6151124	-0.5715831	0.4492318	0.2893650	0.09436923	-0.0219682

Table 5: Document Similarity Matrix after SVD Reduction.

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6
D1	1.0000000	0.2818219	0.8699287	0.6486299	0.9997634	0.2238033
D2	0.2818219	1.0000000	0.7183524	0.9130520	0.3026249	0.9982019
D3	0.8699287	0.7183524	1.0000000	0.9396211	0.8804502	0.6753606
D4	0.6486299	0.9130520	0.9396211	1.0000000	0.6650315	0.8869635
D5	0.9997634	0.3026249	0.8804502	0.6650315	1.0000000	0.2449499
D6	0.2238033	0.9982019	0.6753606	0.8869635	0.2449499	1.0000000

In LSA, the pseudo query doc is also mapped to the reduced vector space as $q_k = \sum_k^{-1} U_k^T q$. Similarity of q_k can be computed with all other documents in reduced V_k matrix. In LSA- information retrieval, similar documents are ranked as per their cosine similarity measures. In LSA-model also notion of relevance ranks in the range of 0 to 1. LSA uses best possible approximation of original matrix A to A_k . Because, SVD - dimensionality reduction is optimal as Frobenius norms $\|A - A_k\| \leq \|A - B\|$, where B is any other matrix whose rank is at the most k .

LSA is an algebraic model and has several shortcomings. It is not a probabilistic model of term occurrences. Also it is not a generative model. Here the topic embeddings are not interpretable and may have arbitrarily positive and negative values as shown in Table 4. Another disadvantage is, LSA needs a very large set of documents and vocabulary to create a model to get accurate results. So LSA model needs to be regenerated after regular intervals so that query documents can relate better with the growing corpus in the internet. Also deciding on the best k value (number of topics) needs some domain knowledge or adjustment. LSA takes care of synonymy problem of English vocabulary but it cannot account for polysemy problem of English language.

LSA has a probabilistic generative variant model named probabilistic latent semantic analysis (pLSA), developed by Thomas Hoffman in 1999 [Hoffman, T 1999]. PLSA uses probabilistic method to generate a model $P(D,W)$ so that for every document d and every word w , probability $p(d, w)$ corresponds to elements in term document matrix. If we assume there are T topics in the corpus having D documents and W unique words, then each document is a probabilistic mixture of topics. For a given document statistical inference of probability of the i^{th} word is :

$$P(w_i) = \sum_{j=1}^T P(w_i|z_{i=j})P(Z_{i=j})$$

, where z_j is the topic of the i^{th} word w_i . Now $P(w|z)$ can be represented as a set of T multinomial distributions, Φ (ϕ), over the W words, such that $P(w|z) = \phi_j^d$, and $P(z)$ can be represented as a set of D multinomial distributions Θ (θ) over the T topics, such that for a word in document d , $P(z=j) = \theta_j^d$. In pLSA, maximum likelihood of ϕ, θ are estimated directly that maximizes $P(w|\theta, \phi)$ by expectation maximization (EM) algorithm. PLSA handles polysemy problem better than LSA. But PLSA is computationally intensive and it has over fitting problem. There is a more well defined generative and Bayesian probabilistic topic model named Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) which is explored in detail in the next section. LDA is also better interpretable by human.

IV.LATENT DIRICHLET ALLOCATION (LDA)

LDA is a popular topic modeling algorithm more efficient than LSA and pLSA. LDA topic model exploits word correlations and latent semantic schemes [Blei et al., 2003, 2004, 2009, 2012]. LDA is a probabilistic, generative model in which documents can be generated by following probability distribution over topics and then probability distribution over words for each topic. In fact, this process is reverse-engineered for inferring probability of latent topics that explain the observed words in the document the best. LDA is an unsupervised learning model, which generates soft clusters of topics, which overlap as a participating word can belong to more than one topic because of polysemy of English language. LDA (Figure 3) takes original TDM matrix as input and decompose it into two matrices, one term by topic (ϕ matrix) and another topic by document (θ matrix). The diagonal matrix Σ of LSA, is not present in LDA model, thus this model is more human interpretable. Another difference with LSA model is that here the topic probabilities per document in θ_d and word probabilities per topic in ϕ_k matrix are all non-negative numbers and sum up to one.

Figure 3: Latent Dirichlet Allocation.

LDA was developed as a machine learning algorithm by David Blei, Andrew Ng, and Michel Jordon in 2003 [Blei et al., 2003]. LDA is named after eighteenth century mathematician Gaustav Dirichlet. A Dirichlet process is a probability distribution function over a range which itself is a set of probability distribution. Thus Dirichlet process is a distribution over distribution. LDA assumes a document is a mixture of a few unobserved (latent) topics. LDA is similar to pLSA, only here a sparse Dirichlet prior Alpha (α) is assumed for topic distribution per document. This hyper-parameter controls the smoothness of topic mixture in the document. When α is less than one then it favors topic distribution over a few topics for a document out of all the topics in the corpus. Griffith and Steyvers introduced [Griffiths et al., 2004] another symmetric Dirichlet prior Beta (β) to control tightness of a topic. Tightness of a topic means a topic can be described with few numbers of words. Experiment shows good choice of β value is .01 and it controls that each topic uses few words more frequently out of all the words in the vocabulary of the corpus. In LDA a topic has no name but it is automatically detected and interpreted by co-occurrence of words. In LDA, a term can belong to more than one topic with different probability and with different co-occurring terms. LDA also relies on bag of word concept where words ordering are ignored. In LDA, even the topics are exchangeable which allows a coherent generative process for test data which is not possible under pLSA model.

In LDA, conditional dependence structures among model variables are depicted graphically with plate notation as in Figure 4. A plate represents the number of times a node inside a plate is repeated. Like in Figure 4, the big outer plate is labeled D and the node θ_d (topic distribution for document d) in it repeats D times as D is the number of documents in the corpus. The inner plate is labeled N , and node $Z_{d,i}$ repeats $D*N$ times as there are D documents and N words in each document. Similarly node $w_{d,i}$ repeats $D*N$ times. The plate with label K repeats K times as K is the number of topics in the corpus vocabulary. The shaded node $w_{d,i}$ depicts an observed variable word w for documents. All other nodes are un-shaded meaning they are latent and needs to be found out.

Figure 4: LDA Bayesian Belief Network with Plate Notation.

LDA is a Bayesian Belief network. The joint probability of the above Bayesian belief network is : $p(w, z, \theta, \varphi | \alpha, \beta) = p(\theta | \alpha) p(z | \theta) p(\varphi | \beta) p(w | z, \varphi)$. However, we are interested in finding probability of a word in each topic for each document and how LDA algorithm finds it, is described below.

LDA Algorithm for Inferring Topics

LDA model parameters are as follows:

α is the parameter for symmetric Dirichlet prior on the per document topic distribution θ_d

β is the parameter for symmetric Dirichlet prior on the per topic word distribution φ_k

θ_d is multinomial topic distribution of document d

φ_k is multinomial word distribution for topic k

$z_{d,i}$ is the topic for i^{th} word in d^{th} document

$w_{d,i}$ is the i^{th} word in document d

In PLSA model θ and φ are estimated directly by Expectation Maximization algorithm for $P(w|z)$. However, this method has the problem of getting stuck in local maxima. In LDA, instead of directly calculating θ and φ , a posterior distribution of topic z for word w_i i.e. $p(z_i | w_i)$ is estimated by a method called variational inference proposed by Blei in 2003. Griffiths and Steyvers used collapsed Gibbs sampling [Griffiths, T. et al., 2004] for the same, which gives better accuracy. Gibbs sampling is a kind of Markov chain Monte Carlo process, which finds out the posterior topic for each word in the original term document matrix by sampling two low dimensional θ and φ matrixes where each value is conditioned on all other values. Sampling proceeds sequentially until the conditional distributions in θ and φ corresponds to target distribution. The probability $p(z_{i=j} | z_{-i}, w_i, d_i, \cdot)$ means topic of word i is conditioned on all other known word topics (z_{-i}) and alpha and beta constants ($\cdot$) and is calculated as follows:

$$p(z_{i=j} | z_{-i}, w_i, d_i, \cdot) \propto \frac{C_{w_{ij}}^{WT} + \beta}{\sum_{w=1}^w C_{w_{ij}}^{WT} + w\beta} * \frac{C_{d_{ij}}^{DT} + \alpha}{\sum_{t=1}^T C_{dt}^{DT} + T\alpha}$$

The above equation has two parts φ and θ . In the left part, $C_{w_{ij}}^{WT}$ stands for number of times word w_i is assigned to topic j (not including the current instance of w_i) in the word-topic count matrix C^{WT} . In the right part, $C_{d_{ij}}^{DT}$ stands for number of times document containing w_i is assigned to topic j (for other words not including the current instance of w_i) in the document-topic count matrix C^{DT} . The count matrices are translated to probability values by dividing by the denominators. The above equation says that a topic value j , which ranges from integer 1 to k will be assigned to a word, depending on its right hand side probability values after checking all k options. In Gibbs sampling algorithm, initially words are assigned to random topics. Then count matrix C^{WT} and C^{DT} are sampled and a new topic for word i is estimated as per the above equation and C^{WT} and C^{DT} are updated. The initial iterations are poor estimate of topic assignment to words but later it converges when count matrix C^{WT} and C^{DT} do not change any more.

LDA generative model is given in Table 6.

Table 6: LDA Generative Model

<p>For each topic k, draw a distribution over words i.e. $\varphi_k \sim \text{Dir}(\beta)$ For each document d, a). Draw a vector of topic proportion $\theta_d \sim \text{Dir}(\alpha)$ b). For each word i i). Draw a topic assignment $z_{d,i} \sim \text{Mult}(\theta_d), z_{d,i} \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ ii). Draw a word $w_{d,i} \sim \text{Mult}(\varphi_{z_{d,i}}), w_{d,i} \in \{1, \dots, V\}$</p>

Basic LSA model uses word frequency for word co-occurrence measurement and failed to incorporate polysemy problem of English language. LDA topic model uses likelihood measure of words in measuring word co-occurrence and tackled the polysemy problem better for finding document similarity. For the original term document matrix in Table 1 having six documents and eight unique words, LDA model has produced the following θ and φ matrix as shown in Table 7. The chosen value of number of topics k here is two. We can see all probability values here are positive and so better interpretable by human.

Table 7: LDA Output.

Document by Topic Matrix: θ								
			1	2				
D1	0.5094340	0.4905660						
D2	0.4905660	0.5094340						
D3	0.5185185	0.4814815						
D4	0.4909091	0.5090909						
D5	0.4629630	0.5370370						
D6	0.4909091	0.5090909						

Topic by Term Matrix: ϕ								
	ocean	sea	water	boat	ship	fish	whale	shark
1	0.009259259	0.009259259	0.28703704	0.287037037	0.379629630	0.009259259	0.009259259	0.009259259
2	0.209459459	0.209459459	0.07432432	0.006756757	0.006756757	0.141891892	0.141891892	0.209459459

Topic stability: In LDA, the original TDM is randomly initialized where words are assigned to random topic numbers. The difference between two Gibbs samples with different random initialization after a number of iterations, is difference in topic probabilities for the same document taken from two different Gibbs sample. Experiments show that large percentage of topics stabilizes and they show same word distribution over topics even when the initialization was different.

Information Retrieval: Document similarity in LDA model is measured according to topic distribution similarity between two documents $d1$ and $d2$. Previously cosine similarity measure was used for this purpose. However, here as we are dealing with probability distribution values another standard measure of similarity called Kullback Liebler (KL) Divergence distance is used. If p and q are two probability distribution of topics between two documents $d1$ and $d2$ then KL Divergence $D: \sum_{j=1}^T p_j \log_2 \frac{p_j}{q_j}$. KL divergence is zero when two probability distributions are exactly same for all topics j . As KL divergence is asymmetric it is also expressed as: $KL(p, q) = \frac{1}{2}[D(p, q) + D(q, p)]$. Similarity of a query to other documents in the corpus can be measured this way. A second approach is to maximize the probability of the query given the document, i.e. $p(q|d_i)$ where $p(q|d_i) = \prod_{w_k \in q} p(w_k|d_i) = \prod_{w_k \in q} \sum_{j=1}^T P(w_k|z=j)p(z=j|d_i)$.

V.LITERATURE REVIEW ON APPLICATION OF TOPIC MODEL

LDA algorithm for topic discovery is relatively new. It can also be extended for achieving higher accuracy for domain specific tasks. Literature reports some extended LDA models like correlated topic model (CTM), author topic model (ATM) and hierarchical topic model (HTM) etc. In this section, literature review for applications of LDA topic model and its variations are explored from the period 2003 till now. LDA model has been extensively studied in the last two decades and widely applied with minor modification and extension for various text analytics tasks. References [Blei, D., 2012], and [Liu, A. 2012] reports topic modeling is a useful tool for digital humanities. Application of computational tools to humanities discipline makes new kinds of research possible. It helps to analyze, summarize, visualize, and theorize a large corpus. The authors in reference [Goldstein, A. et al., 2014] have produced a LDA model of 150 topics from the corpus of 21, 367 articles of 13, 221 authors. They say computational and quantitative topic modeling algorithm is a new way to explore literary history. Topic modeling can capture better long-term trend vs. rapid transformation of linguistic vocabulary. Their topic model also found that themes of social sciences have risen to prominence in the last three decades of literary history.

References [Arnold, C.W. et al., 2010], [Howes, C. et al., 2013], [Lehman, W. et al., 2012], [Ghassemi, M. et al., 2014], and [Resnik, P. et al., 2015] report applications of topic model in scientific dataset of biology, gene science, medicine and weather data. They say clinical concepts can be clustered from patient data and case based retrieval is more efficient using LDA in biological data. Prediction of patient satisfaction and mortality rate is another application. In [Resnik, P. et al., 2015], LDA has been used to cluster words used by depressed patients vs. not depressed patients. In [Bhattacharjee et al., 2016], LDA topic model is applied on medical electronic patient record and co-occurrence of medical conditions are verified with actual records. The topics are evaluated with two measures, tightness and distinctiveness. If a topic can be represented with only a few medical conditions having probability value more than a threshold then the topic is tight. Distinctiveness of topics is measured with Jensen-Shannon Divergence (JSD). There model shows LDA model is capable of finding both tight and distinctive topics from patient records.

References [Liu, B., 2015], and [Lucie, S., 2018] review research area on customer voice or sentiment analysis for products and services. They have also explored applications of many variations of the standard LDA model. Textual comments by customers from various data sources like online survey forms, social media posts and email communication can be analyzed for aspect and personality detection of customers.

This kind of business intelligence extraction from unstructured data of various sources helps businesses to take measures towards customer satisfaction and decision on marketing strategy more efficiently. LDA model has been modified for use of sentiment analysis for increased precision for specific tasks. One such variation is multi grain MG-LDA, which captures both global and local topics. Here local topics relates to ratable aspects. Another variation is supervised SLDA used for classification and regression problem. Another variation is joint sentiment topic model (JST) where topics are conditioned on sentiment polarities. Another variation is maximum entropy LDA, which detects aspects and aspect specific opinion words.

In the literature, along with natural language processing there are numerous applications of LDA topic model for image data and video data analysis as well. Today internet is a vast collection of images such as COREL database, which also needs to be searched. Image retrieval is also based on text query. If the images are already annotated with text then it is possible to retrieve them. However, manual annotation of images is time consuming and not feasible. So, automatic image annotation is an important field of research of computer vision. Images can be annotated with few theme of the picture like “mountain”, “water” “grass” etc. In reference [Feng, Y., et al., 2008, 2010], authors have experimented with automatic image annotation from image content, accompanying caption and the text in which the pictures were embedded. For example, BBC news articles have images embedded in them. Their experiment can also suggest an appropriate image from the collection of stock images for a text document illustration. Co-occurrences of image features such as average and standard deviations of RGB values, LAB values, output of DCT and Gabor filtering, image edge orientation etc. of image regions and words via latent topics are needed for image annotation. Their experiments show that when LDA topic model is used for word ranking for image annotation it outperforms in precision, recall and F-score than other methods used for the same purpose.

LDA has been applied for generating automatic text summary rapidly and has been proven very effective. Single document or multiple documents summary is often needed for quick review and understanding. Large volume of text summarization by human is very time consuming and not feasible. A summary is a text, which is at most half the size of original text and keeps the essence of the original text. Summaries are of two types, extractive and abstractive. LDA algorithm can be applied for extractive summary generation. In extractive summary, important words or phrases or sentences are extracted from a document. As the number of topics in LDA is much lower than number of words, it helps in dimensionality reduction. In addition, sentence to sentence similarity and document to document similarity can be computed more efficiently. When per document topic distribution is known, then first few words of each topic can create an extractive summary of the document. The summary created by machine can be compared with human generated summary and evaluated as ROUGE (Recall Oriented Understudy of Gisting Evaluation) measure. In reference [Tiedan et al. 2012], authors have experimented with similarity based automatic text summarization of news articles using LDA. ROUGE2 and ROUGE4 score of their experiments with LDA are higher than other methods of text summarization. In reference [Nagwani, 2015] they have used LDA topic modeling over the framework of Big data MapReduce for processing huge volume of text in parallel. MapReduce provides faster implementation speed because of distributed parallel processing framework suitable for Big data analytics.

VI. LDA TOPIC MODEL EVALUATION/ EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

In this section, a larger size LDA model is produced for analysis. The input data used is National Institute of Health (NIH) database’s sample project proposal files for funding applications. The LDA topic model is generated using R topic model library [R Library: Topic Models, 2016]. R topic-model package takes document term matrix (DTM) as input and outputs a LDA model. In this experiment fifty topics are generated by setting $k = 50$. Example word cloud is shown for two random topics in Table 8.

Table 8: Word Cloud of Two Topics by LDA

It can be seen that the two topic clusters generated in Table 8, are quite different from each other. It also converged quickly after few thousands of iterations. Table 9 depicts most frequently used topic terms and their Beta (β) values for twelve topics.

Table 9: Term vs. Beta Values for Several Topics

LDA is an unsupervised learning method and the evaluation of the model is subjective. Knowing the best number of topics or k value, needs domain knowledge. Also the model constant Alpha (α) and Beta (β) that controls document topic distribution and topic word distribution needs to be adjusted to get the best results. There is no good quantitative measure to decide the effectiveness of the output of the LDA model. However, in probabilistic model, perplexity is a measure that tells how well a probability distribution predicts a sample. A low perplexity value is good and it tells the probability distribution predicts the sample well. The perplexity of a discrete probability distribution p is defined as: $2^{H(p)} = 2^{-\sum_x p(x) \log_2 p(x)}$, where $H(p)$ is the entropy of the probability distribution over x number of events. Experiment shows that as the number of topic k increases perplexity decreases. The best value of k ranges from 100-300. The best value of Dirichlet prior Alpha (α) = .1 and Beta (β) = .01. Table 10 depicts how perplexity value of the LDA model decreases as number of topics k is increased and it saturates after some k value.

Table 10: Perplexity vs. Number of Topic 1

VII.CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

For people all over the world, single most important thing daily is information retrieval from the internet. This has motivated this paper to look into the details of information retrieval techniques that filter relevant information from the huge collection in the internet. Here LSA and LDA topic models are explored with fair amount of mathematical background as well as conceptual description. For dimensionality reduction and efficient topic modeling LDA algorithm is a most effective recent development. Google like search engine is also implementing LDA topic model. LDA model reduces both synonymy and polysemy problem of English language better than other models.

LDA being a probabilistic Bayesian network, is easy to extend for more specific purposes for increased precision. In future I am going to explore in detail other extended LDA models like correlated topic model (CTM), author topic model (ATM) and hierarchical topic model (HTM) etc. and study how they are applied for text summarization and classification. Topic modeling can be used not only for natural language processing but also for image and video data. Its application domain is varied including humanities, biological, medical and weather dataset. This paper will help researchers in understanding topic modeling easily and in applying it in their respective field of work. LDA being a relatively new model deserves further research for other variations.

REFERENCES

1. R. Feldman, and J. Sanger. 2007. The text mining handbook: Advanced Approaches in Analyzing Unstructured Data. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
2. D. Blei, A.Y. Ng, and M.I. Jordan. 2003. Latent Dirichlet Allocation. In Journal of Machine Learning Research, 3, 993-1022.
3. Wikipedia. 2011. Information Retrieval. URL http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Information_retrieval. (accessed on: 2019-07-28).
4. S. Deerwester, S. Dumais, G. Furnas, T.K. Landauer. 1990. Indexing by Latent Semantic Analysis. In Journal of the American Society for Information Science.
5. Thomas Hofmann. 1999. Probabilistic Latent Semantic Indexing. In Proceedings of the 22nd Annual International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Informational Retrieval, ACM.
6. D. M. Blei, T. L. Griffiths, M. I. Jordan, and J. B. Tenenbaum. 2004. Hierarchical Topic Models and the Nested Chinese Restaurant Process. In Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
7. D. M. Blei, and J. D. Lafferty. 2009. Topic Models. In Text Mining: Classification, Clustering, and Applications., 10(71), 34, Chapman & Hall/CRC.
8. D. M. Blei. 2012. Topic modeling and digital humanities. In Journal of Digital Humanities, 2(1), 8-11.
9. T.L Griffiths, and M. Steyvers. 2004. Finding Scientific Topics. In Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America (PNAS), 101 (Supplement 1): 5228-5235.
10. A.Liu. 2012. The state of the digital humanities: A report and a critique. Arts and Humanities in Higher Education , 11 (1-2), 8-41.
11. A.Goldstone, and T. Underwood. 2014. The Quiet Transformations of Literary Studies: What Thirteen Thousand Scholars Could Tell Us. In New Literary History, 45(3), 359-384.
12. C. W. Arnold, S. M. El-Saden, A. T. Bui, and R. Taira. 2010. Clinical Case-Based Retrieval Using Latent Topic Analysis, In Proceedings of the AMIA Annual Symposium, 26-30.
13. C. Howes, M. Purver, and R. McCabe. 2013. Investigating Topic Modeling for Therapy Dialogue Analysis. In Proceedings of the IWCS Workshop on Computational Semantics in Clinical Text (CSCT), 7-16.
14. W. Lehman, M. Saeed, W. Long, J. Lee, and R. Mark. 2012. Risk Stratification of ICU Patients Using Topic Models Inferred from Unstructured Progress Notes. In Proceedings of the AMIA Annual Symposium, 505-511.
15. M. Ghassemi, T. Naumann, F. Doshi-Velez, N. Brimmer, R. Joshi, A. Rumshisky, and P. Szolovits. 2014. Unfolding Physiological State: Mortality Modelling in Intensive Care Units. In Proceedings. of the 20th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, 75-84.
16. P. Resnik, W. Armstrong, L. Claudino, T. Nguyen, V. A. Nguyen, and J. Boyd-Graber. 2015. Beyond LDA: exploring supervised topic modeling for depression-related language in Twitter. In Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on Computational Linguistics and Clinical Psychology, 99-107.
17. Y. Feng, and M. Lapata. 2008. Automatic Image Annotation using Auxiliary Text illustration. In Proceedings of the Annual Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL'08), 272-280.
18. Y. Feng, and M. Lapata. 2010. Topic Models for Image Annotation and Text Illustration. In Proceedings of the Annual Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL'10), 831-839.
19. C. Howes, M. Purver, and R. McCabe. 2013. Investigating Topic Modeling for Therapy Dialogue Analysis. In Proceedings of the IWCS Workshop on Computational Semantics in Clinical Text (CSCT), 7-16.
20. M. Bhattacharjee, and C. Jurkowitz. 2016. Identifying Patterns of Associated-Conditions Through Topic Models of Electronic Medical Records. IEEE Explore.
21. CRAN. 2016. R library: Topic Models . URL: <https://cran.rproject.org/-web/packages/topicmodels/index.html>, (last accessed Apr. 2016).
22. G. M. Namata, P. Sen, M. Bilgic and L. Getor. 2009. Collective Classification for Text Classification. In Book Text mining: Classification, clustering, and applications, Taylor and Francis Group, LLC.

- 23.** B. Grun, and K. Hornik. 2011. Topicmodels: an R Package for Fitting Topic models. In Journal of Statistical Software, 0(13).
- 24.** L. Spervkova. 2018. Review of Latent Dirichlet Analysis Methods Usable in Voice of Customer Analysis, ACTA Informatica Pragensia, University of Economics, Prague, 2, 152-165.
- 25.** B. Liu. 2015. Sentiment Analysis: Mining Opinions, Sentiments, and Emotions. Cambridge University Press, 1-381.
- 26.** Tiedan Zhu and Kan Li. 2012. The Similarity Measure Based on LDA for Automatic Summarization. In Proceedings of the 2012 International Workshop on Information and Electronics Engineering (IWIEE), Elsevier.
- 27.** N. Nagwani. 2015. Summarizing Large Text Collection Using Topic Modeling and Clustering Based on MapReduce Framework. In Journal of Big Data.